

ECTOPARASITES OF *Clarias gariepinus* (BURCHELL 1822) FROM LAGOS LAGOON, NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

The occurrence and prevalence of ectoparasites in *Clarias gariepinus* from Eti-Osa end of Lagos lagoon was investigated. A total of 110 fish specimens were procured from fishermen at four fishing villages in Eti-Osa local government who fish in Lagos lagoon and examined for ectoparasite infestation. Four parasites namely *Crassicutis sp.* (Mante, 1936), *Argulus sp.*, Nematoda and Sanguinicola (Digenean trematode) were isolated. Forty out of 110 fish specimens were infested giving a prevalence rate of 36.36%. Ectoparasite infestation in the females were significantly higher than in the males ($p < 0.05$). The smaller/younger fish were more infested than the bigger/older ones ($p < 0.05$). *Crassicutis sp.* had the highest prevalence, abundance and mean intensity of 33.64, 19600 and 53.95 respectively among all the parasites recovered. The recovery of this parasite from *Clarias gariepinus* in this study seems to be the first scientific report of *Crassicutis sp.* infesting *C. gariepinus*. It equally seems to be the first scientific report of this parasite in Africa. Further studies should be conducted to investigate the pathogenic effect of this parasite on *Clarias gariepinus*. Further studies should equally be carried out to ascertain the occurrence and prevalence of this parasite on *C. gariepinus* in Nigeria. There is also need for molecular studies to be conducted to ascertain the species taxonomy of this parasite.

KEYWORDS: Ectoparasite, Lagos lagoon, Eti-Osa, *Crassicutis sp.*, prevalence.

INTRODUCTION

Fish is important in the development of Nigeria both economically as a source of income and health-wise as a source of first class protein with low cholesterol level in the diets of the populace (Aken' ova, 2000). By virtue of their economic importance to the populace, especially with the rapidly increasing population and consequent increase in protein demand, information on the parasites of fish becomes particularly important as these parasites may affect fish (Kudoro, 1995; Aken' ova 2000). Parasites are organisms which spend part of their lives living on or at the expense of another (Lasce, 1995). Fish parasitic disease outbreak increase production cost due to the cost of treatment, the investment loss in dead fish and decreased growth of fish during and even after disease outbreak (Meyer 1984; Roberts 2001).

The African catfish, *Clarias gariepinus* (BURCHELL 1822) is generally considered to be one of the most important tropical fish species for culture in West Africa (Clay 1979; Hassan *et al.*, 2007). This catfish is widely distributed throughout Africa, inhabiting tropical swamps, lakes and rivers, some of which are subject to seasonal drying (Olufemi *et al.*, 1991). Commercial production of catfish is a rapidly growing industry.

Concurrent with this growth is an increased interest in their parasites (Meyer, 1984; Roberts, 2001). There exists a relative susceptibility of different fish species to infection (Lasce 1995; Roberts 2001). While all types of fish harbour parasites, they are found in some, more frequently than in others depending some times, upon the age of the fish, the size of the fish, the season when the fish are taken and the types of water body where the fish inhabit (Lasce, 1995).

Knowledge of parasitic diseases in Africa is predominantly made up of taxonomic studies. Paperna (1980) observed that most of such information consists of taxonomic studies and taxonomic descriptions of individual parasitic species from occasional collections from museum materials. Literature on the ectoparasites of *Clarias gariepinus* in Nigeria is scarce and ectoparasites reduce the market value of fish because of the visible signs associated with them (Lasce, 1995). The purpose of this study is therefore to determine the occurrence and prevalence of ectoparasites in *Clarias gariepinus* from Eti Osa end of Lagos lagoon.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study Area

The area of study is the Lagos lagoon (figure 1) which lies between longitude 3° 23' and 3° 42' E and between latitude 6° 22' and 6° 38' N. It is about 50km long having two arms linking the Lekki lagoon and hinterland in eastern and northern parts of the lagoon respectively. It stretches for about 257.49 km from Cotonou, Benin republic to the western edge of the Niger Delta. It is separated from the ocean by the low-lying Lekki barrier system and has the influx from Rivers Yewa, Ogun, Oshun and Ona.

The lagoon extends from the coast at Lagos to about 37 km north at Ikorodu and this continues to about 48 km in the east where it narrowed down to form the Lekki lagoon.

The entire Lagos lagoon experiences the wet equatorial type of climate. The rainfall is intense and storms duration increase into the year. (Omotayo *et al.*,1987).

Eti-Osa local government (figure 1) is a water locked area comprising of Victoria Island, Ikoyi, Obalende, Lekki Peninsula, Sangotedo and Ajah areas of Lagos. It is a wetland area bounded on the north by Lagos lagoon, on the west by Apapa and Lagos Island, on the east by Ibeju- Lekki and on the south by the Atlantic Ocean. It is an area characterized by much artisanal fishing and fish farming activities.

One hundred and ten (110) live fish from Eti- Osa end of Lagos lagoon were procured from fresh fish seller at four fishing villages / landings namely Badore, Sangotedo, Ikota and Ikate Elegushi between November 2007 and April 2008. The samples were transported live to the laboratory for analysis in each case. Water samples were collected from each of the sampling sites and analyzed for their physico-chemical parameters using U-22 horiba water monitoring system.

Figure 1: Map of Eti-Osa Local Government Area showing sampling locations and Lagos lagoon.

Fish Examination

The length and weight measurements of the fish specimens were taken prior to examination. The fish were sexed macroscopically. The fins and entire outer body surface of each specimen was examined according to the method described by Lasce (1995) and Roberts (2001). Smears made from scraping of the fins and body surface were mounted on a light microscope and examined under x10 and x40 power magnifications. The operculum of each specimen was opened; the gills were removed and examined using the method described by Lasce (1995) and Roberts (2001). The parasites recovered were stained with Lugol's iodine, fixed in 70% alcohol and

mounted with Canada balsam (Lasce, 1995; Akinsanya *et al.*, 2007.) They were identified based on external morphology and counted. The Parasites were captured with a digital camera.

Data Analysis

The prevalence of ectoparasite infection was estimated using the model:

$$\text{Prevalence (\%)} = \frac{\text{No. of fish host infested}}{\text{Total no. of fish host examined}} \times 100$$

(Akinsanya *et al.*, 2007; Hassan *et al.*, 2007).

The Abundance and mean intensity of ectoparasite were estimated using the following models:

$$\text{Abundance} = \frac{\text{Total no. of individuals of a particular species in a sample of fish examined}}{\text{Total no. of fish host examined}}$$

$$\text{Mean intensity} = \frac{\text{Total no. of individuals of a particular parasite sp. in a sample of fish examined}}{\text{No. of fish host infested}}$$

(Oluseye, 1990).

Statistical analyses of data obtained were carried out using analysis of variance, correlation and chi-square.

RESULTS

Prevalence, Abundance and Mean intensity of each ectoparasite recovered

Four types of parasites were recovered namely *Crassicutis species* (Mante 1936) (Plate 1), *Argulus species*, Nematoda and Sanguinicola (blood fluke; digenean trematode). Table 1 shows the prevalence, abundance and mean intensity of each ectoparasite recovered. *Crassicutis species* had the highest prevalence (33.64%), abundance (19,600) and mean intensity (53.95), followed by Nematoda with prevalence, abundance and mean intensity of 0.91%, 0.009 and 0.03 respectively.

Plate 1: *Crassicutis sp.* recovered from *C. gariepinus* in Lagos lagoon

Table1. Prevalence, abundance and mean intensity of each ectoparasite recovered from *C. gariepinus* in Lagos lagoon.

Parasite	Total no. recovered	No. of fish infested	Abundance	Mean intensity	Prevalence (%)
<i>Crassicutis sp.</i>	2158	37	19,600	53.95	33.64
Nematoda	5	3	0.045	0.13	2.73
<i>Argulus sp.</i>	1	1	0.009	0.03	0.91
Blood fluke	1	1	0.009	0.03	0.91

Sex-parasite infestation of *C. gariepinus* from Lagos lagoon.

Table 2 shows the infestation of ectoparasites according to sex of fish. 17 out of 54 males and 23 out of 56 females were infested.

Table 2. Infestation of ectoparasites on *C. gariepinus* from Lagos lagoon according to sex of fish.

Fish sex	Total no. examined	Number of host infested	Prevalence (%)
Male	54	17	31.48
Female	56	23	41.07
Total	110	40	

There was no correlation between sex and parasite infestation. Prevalence of ectoparasites in females (41.07%) was significantly higher ($p < 0.05$, $t = 31.516$) than in males (31.48%).

Parasite infestation of *C. gariepinus* from Lagos lagoon according to length size.

Table 3 summarizes the length –parasite infestation for *C. gariepinus* from Lagos lagoon. The length class 22.00 cm -28.99 cm had the highest prevalence rate of 55.00% followed by the length class 15.00 cm-21.99 cm. Length classes 36.00 cm-42.99 cm and 43.00 cm-49.99 cm had no ectoparasite.

Table 3: Summary of length –parasite infestation of *C. gariepinus* from Lagos lagoon.

Length class (cm)	No. of fish host examined	No. of fish host infested	Prevalence (%)
15.00-21.99	59	26	44.07
22.00-28.99	20	11	55.00
29.00-35.99	17	3	17.65
36.00-42.99	06	0	0.00
43.00-49.99	08	0	0.00
Total	110	40	

There was a highly significant correlation ($P < 0.01$) between length of fish and parasite infestation.

Ectoparasite infestation on *C. gariepinus* from Lagos lagoon according to location of the body infested.

Table 4 shows the infestation of ectoparasites on *C. gariepinus* from Lagos lagoon based on location of the body paracitized. There were 39 occurrences of parasites on the gills out of 40, whereas parasite was recovered from the body surface only once.

Table 4: Infestation of ectoparasites on *C.gariepinus* based on location of the body paracitized.

Location of the body paracitized	Frequency of occurrence of parasite	Prevalence (%)
Body surface	1	0.9
Fins	0	0.0
Gill	39	35.5
Total	40	

Water Quality

Table 5 shows the result of water quality analysis for Lagos lagoon.

Table 5: Water Quality Parameters of Lagos Lagoon from four sampling sites (Dec. 2007-March 2008).

Parameters	Sampling sites			
	B	I	S	E
Temperature (°C)	32.9± 0.15	32.6± 0.26	29.9± 0.21	29.9± 1.19
Dissolved Oxygen (g/l)	7.7± 0.26	5.3± 0.26	5.0± 0.2	7.7± 0.26
pH	6.6± 0.17	6.6± 0.21	7.1± 0.15	6.9± 0.15
Salinity (%)	0.5± 0.1	1.1± 0.1	1.0± 0.1	0.5± 0.1
Nitrite (mg/l)	0.1± 0.05	0.2± 0.05	0.2± 0.1	0.3± 0.05
Ammonia (mg/l)	0.5± 0.1	0.5± 0.05	0.5± 0.1	0.4± 0.1
Water Hardness (ppm)	60± 4.6	70± 5.6	80± 3.0	65± 5.0

Legend:

B = Badore

I = Ikota

S = Sangotedo

E = Ikate Elegushi

DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

From the present study, Forty (40) fish specimens were parasitized out of a hundred and ten (110) fish specimens examined. This gave a prevalence rate of 36.36%. Some work has been done on parasites of *Clarias gariepinus*. Paperna (1996), reported prevalence of infection by trypanosome in *C. gariepinus* and *Bagrus spp.* in Lake Victoria at 50%. Hassan *et al.*, (2007) worked on the haemoparasites of *Clarias gariepinus* and *Synodontis clarias* from Lekki lagoon, Nigeria and reported low prevalence of infection, 35.24% and 7.2% in *S. clarias* and *C. gariepinus* respectively. Four parasites were found on the external organs of *C. gariepinus* from this study namely *Crassicutis sp.* (Mante, 1936) (plate 1), Nematoda, *Argulus sp.* and Sanguinicola (blood fluke, digenea trematode). *C. gariepinus* had low prevalence rate of Nematode (2.73%). This is consistent with the reports of kudoro (1995) and Oluseye (1990) who reported prevalence rate of Nematode on *C. gariepinus* at 14.81% and 7.4% respectively. The nematodes were recovered from the body surface of the fish. On the other hand, Adikwu and Ibrahim (2004) recorded nematode infestation of *C. gariepinus* intestine at a high prevalence rate of 40.82%. Nematode are common gut parasites of fish, thus its occurrence on the gills of fish from this study could be due to its migration from the gut to gills or entrance of the nematodes with water from the body surface into the opercula chamber. Oluseye (1990) noted that taxonomy of fish nematodes has not been extensively studied. Pal and Ghosh (1985) reported that little attention was paid to nematode in fish culture and they are just on record for academic purpose.

Sanguinicola (blood fluke) a digenea trematode was recovered from the gills of the fish host. The prevalence of infestation was 0.91%. Lasca (1995) reported that the blood fluke Sanguinicola live as adult in the gill arterioles of salmonids and other fish species. The same author also reported that in some cases, they do not cause serious losses of fish, but if large numbers of miracidia leave the gills at a time it can cause extensive gill damage. Eggs

and developing miracidia also interfere with the circulation of blood in the capillaries of the gills, kidney and liver (Lasce, 1995). Adeyemo (2001) investigated the incidence and Pathogenesis of *Clinostomum tilapiae*, a trematode parasite of tilapia and reported the prevalence of this parasite to range between 25.95-88.889% with mean abundance of 1.73 ± 1.22 and mean intensity of 3.14 ± 1.9 among fish farms in Oyo state. This abundance and mean intensity is similar to that obtained in this study with sanguinicola having abundance and mean intensity as low as 0.009 and 0.03 respectively. Adekunle (1989) worked on trematode parasites found in various organs of *Tilapia sp.* collected from Fisheries department fish farm, University of Ibadan and observed the occurrence of the digenean trematode *Clinostomun marginatum* on the skin of Tilapia.

Argulus sp. (fish louse) had very low prevalence rate of 0.91%. The abundance and mean intensity obtained were very low at 0.05 and 0.13 respectively. This is in line with Oluseye (1990) who investigated the parasites and parasitic diseases observed at a fish breeding centre, Ibadan and observed *Argulus* infesting *Clarias gariepinus* at a low prevalence rate of 7.4%. He noted that several species of *Argulus* incidence can lead to transmission of bacterial haemorrhagic septicaemia or at least favours the invasion of disease organisms. *Argulus sp.* was the only parasite recovered from the body surface of *C. gariepinus* in this study. Lasce (1995) noted that *Argulus* is an ectoparasite that moves freely over the surface of fish host feeding on blood, mucus and epithelial cells. This author also reported that fish louse is extremely common, widely distributed and often lacks host specificity.

Crassicutis sp. (Manter, 1936); a digenean trematode was recovered from the gills of *C. gariepinus*. Fernandes and Kohn (2001) worked on some trematode parasites of fish from Parana River, Brazil and redescribed *Crassicutis cichlasomae* infesting the intestine of the cichlid *Geophagus brasiliensis*. Rolbiecki (2007) reported infestation of *Limanda limanda* (Linnaeus 1758) by the digenean trematode *Aporocotyie simplex* (Digenean; Sangunioideae). It was the first record of this parasite from the polish exclusive economic zone of the Baltic Sea. Scholz *et al.*; (1995) studied the biology of *Crassicutis cichlasomea* of cichlid fishes in Mexico and central America and reported that there was no pronounced preference of *C. cichlasomae* adult for the site of their location in the intestine of the definitive host; a slightly higher proportion (41%) of these worms were only found in the anterior third of the gut. Rodney *et al.*; (1996) redescribed *Crassicutis intermedius* (Szidat, 1954) from siluriform fishes in Paraguay and classified it as a member of the family Homalometridae. The recovery of *Crassicutis sp.* from *Clarias gariepinus* in this study seems to be the first scientific report of *Crassicutis sp.* in *Clarias gariepinus*. *Crassicutis sp.* has mainly been reported in fishes of North, Central and South America. The present study equally seems to be the first scientific report of *Crassicutis sp.* in Africa. Probably, this parasite invaded African waters recently from other regions. Perez-ponce *et al.*; (2008) described a new species of *Crassicutis* parasite of *Cichlasoma beani* Jordan (Osteichthyes; cichlasoma) in Mexico, based on morphology and sequences of the ITS1 and 28S ribosomal RNA genes. They reported that the new species *Crassicutis chondhuryi* differs from most of the other nominal species by having testes located in a symmetrical position. They equally reported that this species is morphologically very similar to *C. cichlasomae* (Mante, 1936), but clearly differs from this species because of the constantly symmetrical position of the testes. The *Crassicutis sp.* reported in this study is morphologically very similar to *C. cichlasomae*. However, detailed molecular studies will be required to specifically confirm its taxonomy at species level.

From this study, female fish were more parasitized than males. Females had prevalence rate of 41.07% whereas males had prevalence rate of 31.48%. The analysis of variance for sex was significant ($p < 0.05$, $t = 31.516$). This is consistent with Kudoro (1995) who reported that the female *Clarias gariepinus* was more parasitized than the males having percentage infestation of 52.63% and 47.375% respectively. On the other hand Oluseye (1990) observed males of *C. gariepinus* to be more infested than females at a ratio of 57:43, M:F, though the test was not significant.

Prevalence of ectoparasites according to size showed that length classes 22.00-28.99 cm and 15.00-21.99 cm had the highest prevalence of ectoparasites at 55% and 44.07% respectively. This means that the smaller/younger fish were more infested than the bigger and older ones. The analysis of variance showed that the test is significant for length ($p < 0.05$, $t = 9.06$). There was a high significant correlation ($p < 0.01$, $r = 0.314$) between length of fish (cm) and parasite infestation. The relationship is inverse which implies that the smaller /younger the fish, the more the parasitic infestation. This could be attributed to the fact that younger fish have less immunity against parasites whereas bigger and older fish have fully developed immunity against parasitic infestation. This observation is in consonance with Adeyemo, (2001) who investigated the incidence and pathogenesis of *Clinostomium tilapiae* in Oyo State farms and reported that juvenile fish were more susceptible

to *C. tilapiae* infection. This is also in consonance with Akinsanya *et al.*, (2007) who reported that the smaller cat fish were more infested than the bigger ones. In contrast, Kudoro (1995) studied some parasites of cultured fish and reported that there was a gradual increase in the percentage infestation with increase in length.

The part of fish most infested is the gills. The body surface had ectoparasite occurring in one out of 40 occurrences of parasites and the remaining 39 was on the gills. This gave prevalence of ectoparasite infection of 0.9% and 35.5% for the body surface and gills respectively. The very low occurrence of ectoparasites on the body surface could be attributed to the fact that *Clarias gariepinus* lacks scales and as such offers less hiding and attachment site for parasites on their body surface.

The result of the water quality analysis showed that the physico-chemical parameters of Lagos lagoon (Table 6) are within the recommended range for catfish. Therefore the occurrence and prevalence of ectoparasites on the stock cannot be attributed mainly to poor water quality but could be vertical transmission of the parasites from host to host.

Amongst the four parasites recorded in this study, it was only *Crassicutis sp.* that had high prevalence, abundance and mean intensity. The mean intensity of 53.95 by *Crassicutis sp.* is high and may have a harmful effect on the fish. Further studies should be conducted to investigate the pathogenetic effect of this parasite on *Clarias gariepinus*. Further studies should equally be carried out to ascertain the occurrence and prevalence of this parasite on catfish in Nigeria. There is also need for molecular studies to be carried out to ascertain the species taxonomy of this parasite.

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